

Research paper

Tailored montmorillonite nanoparticles and their behaviour in the alkaline cement environment

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ABSTRACT

This is the first time an analytical protocol is proposed to investigate and live-monitor the behaviour of montmorillonite nanoparticles, of different natures, in alkaline cement environment (pH of 12–13). In this study inorganic and organomodified montmorillonite nanoparticles were characterised via TEM, XRD, SEM-EDX and TGA. The inorganic montmorillonite used consisted of a purified montmorillonite commercially available as HPS-clay, and an organomodified montmorillonite, namely XDB-organoclay, consisted of purified montmorillonite modified with Noramonium MB2HT salt. Both montmorillonite nanoparticles were tailored to increase their compatibility with the hydrating cement environment. This gave rise to three different slurries: (i) reference-slurry, (ii) inorganic-slurry, and (iii) organic-slurry. The slurries were characterised and investigated through UV/vis, to measure suspension quality in terms of physical stability and rheological properties, and by AFM and FTIR to determine the chemical stability. The results indicated that the organic-slurry can offer a good stability, preventing aggregation of the clay particles at the targeted pH (13). The inorganic-slurry showed a reduction in surface charge and increased double layer repulsion. At pH 13 it was possible to obtain dispersion of the reference slurry although it underwent gelation and became viscous. The research findings informed that the inorganic slurry favours miscibility of the montmorillonite nanoparticles with cement particles and offers additional nucleation sites for CSH. Therefore it can be considered an alternative to organomodified montmorillonite as an addition in cement based materials.

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1. Introduction

Montmorillonite (Mt) is a clay mineral of significant commercial importance. This naturally occurring hydrous aluminium silicate exists as an octahedral sheet between two tetrahedral sheets, producing plate-like layers that can be up to a micron or more in diameter and about 1 nm thick. This high aspect ratio platelet structure can confer enhanced physical and mechanical properties when incorporated in cement matrices (Chang et al., 2007). The main focus to-date on Mt use has been as clay polymer nanocomposites (CPN) to confer enhanced mechanical properties and increased functionality (Ataefard and Moradian, 2011). By nature, Mt particles are inorganic, hence, hydrophilic and can readily disperse in water due to the hydration of the basal surfaces, swelling and exfoliating the clay (Birgisson and Dham, 2011; Nehdi, 2014). Generally, dispersion of hydrophilic Mt particles within a CPN is not feasible due to thermodynamic incompatibility of the mineral and organic phases. In which case, surface modification of the particles using an

organic agent is necessary to provide compatibility with the polymeric matrix. The organomodification primarily takes place through cation exchange, replacing metal ions with organic cations such as alkylammonium. As well as conferring compatibility of the clay for the polymeric matrix, the adsorption of fatty surfactant molecules in the interlayer region of platy minerals allows separation of the layers which promotes intercalation of polymer chains into the interlayer space during CPN preparation; the greater the intercalation distance, the easier it is for attractive van der Waals forces to be overcome and full exfoliation into discrete nanoparticles to be achieved (Ouellet-Plamondon et al., 2012). Good particle dispersion is critical in realising the 'nano-effect' provided by the clay addition for optimum performance. Regarding the cement paste environment, in the one hand organomodification of Mt renders it thermodynamically incompatible with the aqueous environment of cement and concrete formulations (Kuo et al., 2006). Nonetheless organomodified Mt (OMt) is expected to enhance water penetration resistance (the hydrophobic Mt does not allow water to enter the interlayer region) and strength development until day 28 in OMt nanoparticles-enhanced cement pastes (Brinkienė et al., 2015). Chloride permeability reduction of OMt nanoparticles-enhanced

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cement mortars can be observed through electrochemical impedance spectroscopy and field emission scanning electron microscopy tests shown an increase in the ionic transport resistance and denser microstructure respectively (He and Shi, 2008). Moreover, water penetration resistance, electrical resistivity and splitting tensile strength can also be improved until day 56 in OMt enhanced concrete (Hosseini et al., 2015). However, further findings suggest that OMt nanoparticles are particularly sensitive to the functional group of modifier used with respect to microstructure and strength development of cement paste-OMt nanoparticle formulations (Kalpokaitė-Dičkuvienė et al., 2015). Exfoliated OMt nanoparticles are preferred in cement pastes and according to Xi exhibits a greater d001-value (Xi, 2006). However, OMt nanoparticles with larger d001-value has been found to increase capillary porosity in hardened cement (Kalpokaitė-Dičkuvienė et al., 2015). Dispersing agents can be used in order to improve compatibility of the hydrophilic environment of the cement paste with the hydrophobic OMt nanoparticles. The water-soluble polyacrylates in addition to the electrostatic stabilising effect, provide steric stabilisation of the clay particles through a combination of elastic and osmotic interactions. The result is an increase in the concentration of particles in suspension. On the other hand there is evidence in recent research that the enhancement of the pozzolanic reaction, of the flexural strength and of the microstructure of composite cement pastes can be more pronounced when inorganic Mt is added in cement pastes rather than OMt slurries with different dispersants (Papatzani and Paine, 2015). In which case, there is good reason to use the unmodified Mt nanoparticles (or inorganically modified Mt with Na⁺ ions to produce purified sodium Mt) in cement and concrete formulations. In aqueous environment clay platelets will readily disperse, with an element of stability afforded to the dispersed particles due to the predominantly negative charge that result from isomorphous substitution of ions within the crystal structure. The negative charges act to stabilise the particles by repulsive interaction that can, in favourable solvent environments, overcome the attractive van der Waals interactions, as described by DLVO theory (Derjaguin et al., 1987). However it is important to mention that hydrophilic Mt nanoparticles may affect durability of cement and concrete due to the presence of alkali metal ions present in the interlayer regions of the un-modified clay that can contribute to destructive alkali-aggregate reactions (West, 1996). Given the significant effect organomodifier and surfactants have on the structure of Mt nanoparticles, the protocol and set of analytical tools proposed in this study was paramount in obtaining information of the tailored Mt nanoparticles behaviour in the alkaline cement environment. In this paper, inorganic (HPS) and organomodified (XDB) Mt nanoparticles in powder form were first characterised via TEM, XRD, SEM-EDX and TGA. Furthermore, the Mt nanoparticles were tailored to cement environment in which three different Mt nanoparticles systems of aqueous dispersions (slurries) were derived. (i) Reference-slurry, (ii) Inorganic-slurry (iii) Organic-slurry. Their behaviour was investigated at various pH environments through atomic force spectroscopy (AFS), Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy, rheology, and spectrophotometry.

2. Materials and methodology

Two types of Mt (raw material) in powder form were used, both of which were supplied by *Laviosa Chimica Mineraria S.p.A*, Italy, and dried before use to remove any residual moisture:

- a purified sodium Mt Named as “HPS-clay” hereafter.
- an organically modified Mt by exchange of basal metal cations with methylbenzyl di-hydrogenated tallow ammonium chloride (Noramonium MB2HT). Named as “XDB-organoclay” hereafter.

Aqueous Mt nanoparticle dispersions were prepared using dispersing agents which were selected based on the nature of the Mt nanoparticle surface:

- (i) Sodium polyacrylate (NaPA) with average molar mass 5100 and used as received (supplied by Sigma Aldrich) was used to aid the dispersion of HPS-clay in aqueous environment.
- (ii) Synperonic 10/6, a non-ionic fatty alcohol/polyethoxy surfactant and used as received (supplied by Croda Chemicals Europe) was employed to disperse XDB-organoclay in aqueous environment. The methodology employed comprised of three steps: characterisation of Mt (raw material); stability of the tailored Mt nanoparticle slurries; and behaviour of the tailored Mt nanoparticles at different pH environments.

2.1. Characterisation of the Mt nanoparticles (raw materials)

Both Mt types, namely HPS-clay and XDB-organoclay, were characterised through the following test regimes:

2.1.1. Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM)

Aqueous dispersions at 10 ng/mL were prepared from the Mt nanoparticles (HPS-clay and XDB-organoclay). These were then deposited onto hydrophilised formvar/carbon films on Copper supports and analysed in a Jeol JEM 1200 mkII. Images were recorded on a Gatan Dual View camera.

2.1.2. X-ray diffraction (XRD)

Measurements were performed using a D8 ADVANCE X-ray diffractometer with CuK α radiation. Spectra were obtained in the range $4^\circ < 2\theta < 60^\circ$. Analysis of reflections and d-value were calculated using EVA software, following Bragg's law ($n\lambda = 2d\sin\theta$) (Ramachandran and Beaudoin, 2001).

2.1.3. Scanning electron microscopy/X-ray energy dispersive spectroscopy (SEM/EDX)

For SEM/EDX. Sample preparation was carried out in two steps. First dispersions of the HPS-clay and XDB-organoclay were prepared (same as for the TEM sample preparation) In the second step HPS-clay and XDB-organoclay dispersions were vacuum dried for three days at a pressure of 10–2 mbar (100 Pa). After that HPS-clay and XDB-organoclay powders were placed on a sheet of molybdenum, an element absent from both Mt types. The equipment used was a Jeol 6480LV.

2.1.4. Thermogravimetric analyses (TGA)

These analyses were carried out using a Setaram TGA92 instrument. Approximately 20 mg of each Mt were placed in an alumina crucible and heated at a rate of 10 °C/min from 20 °C to 1000 °C under 100 mL/min flow of inert nitrogen gas. Mass change, differential mass change and heat flow measurements were recorded and analysed using the built-in software. The differential thermogravimetric curve (dTG) was derived from the TG curve. The first derivative curve was obtained for the various Mt samples and was used for comparisons, instead of the mass loss curve, as it yields sharp distinctive reflections.

2.2. Stability of the tailored Mt nanoparticle slurries

Mt were tailored to remain as discrete nanoparticles within the hydrating cement paste. This is of paramount importance if Mt nanoparticles are to be added to cement based materials to act as nucleation agent for promoting hydration. Three aqueous dispersions were prepared, two of which were aided with the surfactants described in Section 2. The three tailored Mt dispersions' preparation methods can be described as follows: (i) Reference-slurry: HPS-clay aqueous dispersion at 15% mass was prepared by ultrasonication using a Herman dynamic 2000CV 20 kHz ultrasonic processor fitted with a 10 mm diameter sonotrode operating at 100% voltage. This dispersion was water based only, without addition of surfactants

and was used as the base for the other two dispersions. (ii) Inorganic-slurry: NaPA was added to the HPS-clay aqueous dispersion (Reference-slurry) at a ratio to clay particle mass of 0.05 and they were mixed using an overhead stirrer. The inorganic-slurry at 15% mass was then prepared by ultrasonication as above. (iii) Organic-slurry: XDB-organoclay particles were stabilised using Synperonic 10/6 at a ratio to particle mass of 0.25. Again the organic-slurry at 15% mass was prepared by ultrasonication as above.

A range of concentrated solutions from pH 7 to 14 were prepared. At high pH this solution was referred as “synthetic cement pore fluid”, an aqueous solution of 16.00 g/L NaOH, 7.00 g/L K₂SO₄, 18.00 g/L KOH, 0.15 g/L Ca(OH)₂. All tailored Mt nanoparticles namely, Reference-slurry, inorganic-slurry and organic-slurry were mixed with the synthetic cement pore fluid. The purpose of this set of experiments was to evaluate the dispersion stability of the tailored Mt nanoparticles at a simulated pH and electrolyte environment of typical cement hydrating conditions. The stability of the three slurries was evaluated through the following test regime:

2.3. UV/vis attenuation and rheological measurement

Transmission UV/vis (Dr Lange XION 500 Spectrophotometer) measurements of dilute dispersions (approximately 1 mg/cm³) in 1 cm pathlength quartz cuvettes, operating at wavelength 340 nm to 900 nm, allowed mass extinction coefficients to be calculated using the Beer-Lambert relationship. Rheological assessments were carried out using a TA Instruments AR2000 Controlled Stress Rheometer fitted with a cone and plate geometry (2°; 40 mm). The viscosity of the dispersions was measured by subjecting samples to an increasing shear stress, from 1 to 300 Pa over 180 s. Samples were carefully applied to the measuring system 3 min prior to measurement. All measurements were taken at 20 °C.

2.4. Behaviour of the tailored Mt at different pH environments

Atomic force spectroscopy and Fourier transform infrared techniques were employed to investigate the changes in behaviour of the slurries (tailored Mt nanoparticles) in concentrate solutions ranging from neutral to alkaline media (pH 7–14).

2.4.1. Atomic Force Spectroscopy (AFS)

is an accessory derived from atomic force microscopy (AFM) which allows for the investigation of materials at the nanometre scale, providing information about the surface topography. AFS gives more specific information about surface energy therefore it provides measurement of the surface forces through force curves. These interactions were measured using a Digital Instruments Multimode Nanoscope IIIA atomic force microscope. All experiments were conducted in fluid utilising 2 µm (nominal) Si/SiO₂ spherical contact probes. Fig. 1A shows a SEM micrograph of one of the probes used in this study. Force curves were processed using a Nanoscope analysis package (Bruker, USA).

2.4.2. FTIR

(Perkin Elmer Frontier, USA) with a Pike (USA) diamond ATR sampling device was used. Spectra recorded at 2 cm⁻¹ resolution with a DGTS detector and KBR optics. In order to consider wetting of the Mt nanoparticles all spectra were normalised to the Si—O peak and the Si—O—OH peak quantified by calculating the area.

2.4.3. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

Monolithic silicon probes (Nanosensors model SD-Sphere-CNT-M-10 from Windsor Scientific, UK) and Muscovite Mica substrates (Agar Scientific, UK) were immobilised on to adhesive conductive carbon tape (Agar Scientific, UK) and observed using a Jeol 6301F field emission. The probe lever dimensions were 400 µm × 20 µm × 5 µm (Fig. 1A). The radius of curvature of the tip of the probe showed a

Fig. 1. A) SEM image of the AFS monolithic silicon probe. B) SEM image of the AFS probe functionalised with clay showing the radius of curvature (after a measurement).

slightly increase (Fig. 1B). This is because the probe picked some material up during the course of an experiment.

For each one of the tailored Mt nanoparticle slurries a set of silicon probe and mica substrate was functionalised. Prior functionalisation probe and substrate went through the following process: (i) first of all probes were cleaned in an aqueous solution of HCl (5%); (ii) After which they were rinsed thoroughly. (iii) cleaned probes, freshly cleaved substrates and a heated pan with the adhesive cyanoacrylate were placed in a sealed nitrogen purged chamber; (iv) the adhesive (in vapour form) was allowed to be deposited on the surface of the probes and substrates for the duration of 1 min; (v) the final step consisted in removing probes and substrates from the nitrogen purging chamber and placing them in a chamber with a saturated vapour of acetone to soften the adhesive. This procedure facilitated the bonding of the tailored Mt nanoparticle dispersions onto the surfaces of the probe and substrate. For the purpose of the AFS experiments the tailored Mt nanoparticle slurries (described in Section 2.2) were further diluted in water (at 0.05% wv). For the functionalisation, probes and substrates were immersed separately in each one of the three diluted slurries for 30 s. This allowed for the tailored Mt nanoparticles to self-assemble onto the probe tip and substrate surface. The functionalised probe tip and substrate surface were then rinsed three times, in distilled water, to remove unbound clay. Care was taken to keep the samples wet with water/buffer until the time of the experiment. The fluid cell was similarly cleaned and allowed to equilibrate for 2 h prior to assembly of each system (functionalised probe and substrate). It is important to notice that probe tip (Si/SiO₂ spherical) and substrate (Muscovite mica) were functionalised under the same conditions for each given tailored Mt nanoparticle slurry.

Fig. 2. TEM micrographs (A and B) HPS-clay particles agglomerates at different magnifications. (C) TEM-Diffraction pattern of the region shown in A of HPS-clay. XDB-organoclay at different magnifications (D) at 100000 \times and (E) at 60000 \times .

3. Results and discussion

Firstly the nano and microstructure characterisation of the two types of Mt nanoparticles namely, HPS-clay and XDB-organoclay was carried

out. Secondly the stability of the tailored Mt nanoparticles (Reference-slurry, Inorganic-slurry and Organic-slurry) was investigated. In the final step the behaviour of the tailored Mt in the synthetic cement fluid was evaluated.

Fig. 3. (A) XRD pattern of the HPS-clay. (B) XRD pattern of XDB-organoclay.

3.1. Characterisation of the Mt nanoparticles

The nanostructure of the Mt was observed by TEM. In Fig. 2(A and B) a typical agglomeration of HPS-clay nanoparticles shows that the bulk of the Mt did not exfoliate. Nevertheless on the edges of the agglomerates (Fig. 2A and B) it was possible to identify regions in which the clay nanoparticles were partially exfoliated (this could be attributed to the industrial purification of the Mt). The HPS-clay particle size was observed to be approximately 500 nm in diameter (Fig. 2A) and the average thickness was approximately 40 nm. The latter value may be attributed to the tendency of the HPS-clay particles to agglomerate on drying.

The diffraction pattern of the HPS-clay, with the presence of rings, showed a polycrystalline structure with randomly oriented grains (Fig. 2B and C). This pattern reinforces the view that this clay was partly exfoliated (Fig. 2C). The grouping pattern of the defined white dots indicates an extremely ordered single crystal, most probably calcite, an impurity commonly found in the mineralogical composition of Mt. The presence of calcite in the Mt was confirmed by XRD analysis (Fig. 3). The calculation of the lattice reflection is given by the following adapted formula (Goodhew, 1975):

$$\frac{r}{2L} = \frac{\lambda}{d} \rightarrow d = \frac{2\lambda L}{r} \quad (1)$$

where L : the camera length and λ : the electron wavelength, which are independent of the specimen and constant for the TEM instrument and $d = d$ -value and $r =$ distance from the diffraction centre. Since d is inversely proportional to r , the largest d -value is obtained by the innermost ring. For the specific TEM diffraction analysis, $\lambda L = 1$. These results can be compared with d -value measured by XRD. The various d -value were calculated by the diffraction pattern (Fig. 2C) according to

Eq. (1). The values obtained were: $d_1 = 1.14$ nm; $d_2 = 0.56$ nm; $d_3 = 0.38$ nm; $d_4 = 0.32$ nm and $d_5 = 0.28$ nm. TEM imaging of XDB-organoclay (Fig. 2D and E) showed larger clusters than the HPS-clay, with very dense agglomerates (for example, the black region at the top of Fig. 2E). The distinctive black dots (Fig. 2E) represent clusters of organic matter. The TEM diffraction pattern of XDB-organoclay (Fig. 2F) showed a poorly crystalline structure with only a few rings and no white dots. It can be inferred in this case that the XDB-organoclay particles exfoliated but that they also agglomerated. From this it can be deduced that they were not well dispersed. The various d -value were calculated by the diffraction pattern (Fig. 2F) according to Eq. (1). The values found were as follows: $d_1 = 3.7$ nm; $d_2 = 2.86$ nm; $d_3 = 1.57$ nm; $d_4 = 0.92$ nm and $d_5 = 0.8$ nm. XRD diffraction patterns were obtained by the D8 ADVANCE X-ray diffractometer. HPS-clay diffractogram is presented in Fig. 3A. The d_{001} -value measured by this technique was equal to 1.22 nm which can be attributed to the d_{001} -value of the Mt (Sapalidis et al., 2011), indicating a monolayer structure (de Paiva et al., 2008). The broader reflections at 20.0° , 35.0° and 54.1° 2θ are attributed to the typical Mt clay structure which shows the amorphous and poorly crystalline structure of the aluminosilicate (Chang et al., 2007). The reflection at 26.8° 2θ is associated with quartz, the reflection at 28.7° 2θ is associated with feldspar and the one at 29.6° 2θ with calcite, typically traced in the chemical composition of Mt (He et al., 1996; Temini et al., 1998). The intermediate reflections between 40° and 55° 2θ can be associated to Mg-Al-silicate according to He et al. (1996). It is acknowledged that calcite has a reflection between 29.3° – 29.4° 2θ and quartz at about 26.6° – 26.7° 2θ , indicating an angular error on the diffraction traces. Therefore, a 0.2° 2θ correction should be applied to the data presented in Fig. 3A.

The XRD diffraction pattern of XDB-organoclay can be seen in Fig. 3B. The increase in d_{001} -value from 1.07–1.32 as found in most Mt (LeBaron et al. 1999, Hedley et al. 2007, de Paiva et al. 2008) to a value of 3.55 nm at 2.5° 2θ for the XDB-organoclay reflects the gallery expansion of the organomodification process. The broader reflections at 19.9° , 34.9° and 54.0° 2θ are attributable to the amorphous and poorly crystalline structure of the aluminosilicate (Mt) (Chang et al., 2007). The reflection at 27.3° 2θ is associated with quartz or feldspar and that at 29.9° 2θ to calcite (Fernandez et al., 2011; He et al., 1996). The presence of higher order reflections (d_{002} -value and d_{003} -value) suggests the organic modifier chains are regularly stacked in the interlayer space (Fig. 3B). Elemental characterisation was obtained through the SEM-EDX analyses. For statistical reliability of the elemental analysis a matrix (5×5) spectra of randomly selected sites was obtained for both HPS-clay and XDB-organoclay. The HPS-clay contained only small quantities of carbon (2.7%), and significant quantities of silicon (16.4%), aluminium (6.4%) and oxygen (70.0%). XDB-organoclay contained low quantities of silicon (5.7%), aluminium (2.0%), and oxygen (31.0%) and high quantities of carbon (60.5%), as would be expected of an organo modified

Fig. 4. Comparison of dTG of HPS-clay and XDB-organoclay.

Fig. 5. Viscosity-shear rate behaviour of (A) reference slurry (0% NaPA) and inorganic-slurry (dispersed in water over a range of NaPA concentrations). (B) XDB organo-tailored dispersions exposed to simulated cement pH and electrolyte environment. Curves have been expanded to clarify differences in viscosity at high shear (inset).

clay. It should be noted that not all elements were detected for all spectra. In general, the elemental analyses of the HPS-clay and the XDB-organoclay revealed that; the Si/Al ratio of HPS-clay was between 3.2 and 3.6 with a median of 3.5 and a standard deviation of 0.1. The Si/Al ratio of XDB-organoclay was higher than that of HPS-clay, and typically fell between 3.7 and 4.4 with a median of 3.9 and a standard deviation of 0.2, much higher than that of HPS-clay. Therefore it can be inferred that the HPS-clay was more homogeneous than the XDB-organoclay. Thermal gravimetry analyses (Fig. 4) showed that the HPS-clay exhibited a substantial mass loss, of approximately 10%, related to adsorbed water (at around 110 °C). A second mass loss was detected at onset temperature of approximately 400 °C and peaking between 600 °C and 700 °C. This indicates the presence of chemically bound water, observed here as dehydroxylation of the clay mineral (Xi et al., 2005). For the XDB-organoclay, the mass loss up to 180 °C was minor, indicating that the organomodification was successful rendering the clay with hydrophobic properties. Thermal analysis of XDB-organoclay reveals very little water, either present as physically adsorbed or chemically bound water. The dehydroxylation shown at ~600 °C for the HPS-clay is entirely absent for the XDB-organoclay (Fig. 4). The thermal decomposition of the organomodifier can be identified by the substantial loss of mass, approximately 44%, in the temperature range of 150 °C to 500 °C.

3.2. Stability of the tailored Mt nanoparticle slurries

Slurries of the two clay types (HPS-clay and XDB-organoclay) were prepared in order to render the Mt nanoparticles discrete in alkaline

environment. The stability of the three tailored Mt namely, reference-slurry, inorganic-slurry, and organic-slurry was investigated.

3.3. Reference and inorganic-slurries

HPS clay dispersed in water without dispersing aid displayed very high viscosity over much of the experimental shear rate (Fig. 5A); making it very difficult to obtain a well dispersed suspension. The addition of a relatively low concentration of NaPA had a dramatic effect upon suspension rheology, reducing viscosity over the entire shear rate range. This has allowed for the determination of an optimum dispersant concentration, expected to be that which provides the lowest viscosity for the dispersed particles, or the point at which increased dispersant concentration provides no further substantial benefit to viscosity reduction and hence dispersion stability (Fig. 6). Using this technique it was concluded that a ratio of NaPA to HPS of 0.05 provides optimum dispersion stability. Despite the rheological effect of the apparent improvement in HPS-clay dispersion quality with the addition of the dispersing aid, addition of polyacrylate (NaPA) appears to have had little impact upon the size of the dispersed particles, (Fig. 7A). Addition of the reference slurry in the synthetic cement pore fluid had a dramatic effect upon the sedimentation stability of this system. Whilst HPS-clay dispersed in deionised water with NaPA (inorganic slurry) or without (reference slurry) – and remained in suspension indefinitely, complete phase separation of the HPS-clay particles occurred overnight in the synthetic cement pore fluid when left undisturbed. This can be attributed to the screening of the surface electrostatic charge of the particles in the high polyelectrolyte environment of the pore fluid, resulting in reduction in the magnitude of the charge to the extent that it became insufficient to overcome interparticle attractive forces and subsequent agglomeration of the individual platelets into larger particles. These larger particles are prone to sedimentation under gravity, although this sediment was quite easily redispersed by applying gentle shear. The effect upon UV/vis attenuation behaviour of the remixed sample was less dramatic, although particle size had clearly been affected, as inferred by the flattening of the attenuation curve in Fig. 7A.

Fig. 6. Comparison of viscosity and NaPA concentration for 10% mass HPS-clay dispersed in water at shear rate of (a) 0.01 s⁻¹ and (b) 10 s⁻¹.

Fig. 7. (A) Comparison of UV/vis attenuation of the Reference-slurry and Reference-slurry dispersed in synthetic cement pore fluid and deionised water environments. (B) Comparison of UV/vis attenuation curves for XDB organo-tailored dispersion before and after exposure to synthetic cement pore fluid environment.

3.4. Behaviour of the tailored Mt nanoparticles at different pH environments

The three tailored-Mt nanoparticle systems comprised of a set of probe-substrate each, functionalised with a given tailored Mt nanoclay (Table 1). Each of the three systems was evaluated through a pH range of 7 to 13. The behaviour of the tailored Mt nanoparticle systems was recorded and measured by means of atomic force and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy, AFS and FTIR respectively.

AFS data collection comprised of 600 force curves of which 200 nominal spectra were averaged to produce a typical interaction force. The residual 400 comprised of >1 monolayer of tailored Mt nanoparticle. In order to simplify interpretation of the complex AFS data, the curve was divided into three main stages: (i) the approach – this is the distance from where the first deflection was detected to where the probe started to bend linearly, indicating (ii) a compliance regime that extended to where the probe either met the surface and/or where the surface layers were no longer compressible and the probe became saturated. Compliance is the equivalent of elastic modulus for the Mt nanoparticles arrangement (e.g. houses of cards) and not the Mt nanoparticle

Table 1
Tailored Mt nanoparticle systems.

Systems (probe-substrate)	Tailored Mt nanoparticle
System-ref	Reference-slurry
System-inorganic	Inorganic-slurry
System-organic	Organic-slurry

themselves. It is the distance which the Mt nanoparticle layer could be compressed indicating the degree of expansion and ability to be compressed and interdigitated; (iii) the retract path from where the compliance curve (plastic/elastic behaviour) ceased and electrostatic (adhesion/repulsion force) dominated. For each force exerted, a distance was recorded. Distances are given in nanometres (nm) and forces in nanonewtons (nN) (per 100 nm², contact area of the probe and Mt nanoparticles). The results of the AFS experiments are presented in Fig. 8. Which show the cantilever response upon approach and retraction of the probe tip over a pH range of 7 to 13 for the three different tailored Mt nanoparticle systems.

Fig. 8. (A) Mean AFS force and distance curves for system-ref. (B) Mean AFS force and distance curves for system-inorganic. (C) Mean AFS force and distance curves for system-organic.

Fig. 9. Behaviour of three tailored Mt nanoparticle systems and their dispersion stability in fluid (pH 13).

When the reference-slurry underwent pH environments of 9–10 (Fig. 8A), there was an increase in the approach, compliance, retract peak forces and all relevant distances. Repulsion on the approach and adhesion on the retract could also be observed. Around the targeted pH range of 12–13, which is typical of what would be experienced by the particles in a cement formulation, the compliance distance was in the order of 20 nm even though during approach and retract a drop in the peak force was detected. This is an indication that reference-slurry Mt nanoparticle has a reduced expansion when compared to HPS inorganic-tailored Mt nanoparticle. This weak interaction may be a result of a densely packed 'stack of cards' structure (Fig. 9), although the electrostatic double layer repulsion is still evident. Reduced compliance force indicates slippage between the platelets. There was a reduced expansion and consequently high attractive interactions in the rheology evaluation as high viscosity of the HPS-clay in water without dispersing agent (Figs. 5A and 6).

The limited effect upon particle stability at high pH was observed in the UV/vis curves presented in Fig. 7A, although this was in the presence of high electrolyte concentration also. The interaction between the functionalised probe and substrate with HPS inorganic-tailored Mt nanoparticle is shown in Fig. 8B. Upon approach of the functionalised probe tip towards the functionalised substrate (Mica) surface, neither adhesion nor repulsion were detected. Upon retraction, a sharp adhesion at pH 9 was observed, followed by a decline in adhesive interaction at pH 10. This was followed by another peak at pH 11, albeit at a much reduced force of 3nN. In the pH range of 12–13, there was no adhesion

and the increasing compliance distance indicated the expansion of the layers, although at this pH range there was no net increase in the adhesion or repulsion. This apparent repulsive effect would support a stiff, expansive 'house of cards' structure (i.e. large volume filling but weak interaction between the platelets) (Fig. 9). Again, this maintained particle stability was observed in the UV/vis evaluation of particles in the concentrated slurry in synthetic pore fluid in Fig. 7A. Inspection of the retraction peak force curve generated by the interaction between the XDB organo-tailored Mt nanoparticle (Fig. 8C) reveals that at low pH there was a long range adhesion between the organic modifier and the surfactant (Synperonic).

However when the pH reached 10 the adhesion decreased and this effect was reduced to zero. Moreover at around pH 12, an increase in the compliance force of the layers was witnessed, which appears optimal, similarly indicating a more energetic organisation i.e. one that can resist lateral slip (cohesive, densely packed 'deck of cards' structure). Furthermore, there was also no net adhesion on retraction around the target pH of 13; the distance at which the forces were felt had been reduced. Overall this suggests that the surfactant (Synperonic) was effective in neutralising the long range forces. However on compression the layers neither slipped nor compressed much, indicating a low space volume. This effect could be explained by some inertial resistance to slip due to the lack of compliance on deformation. Practically, this effect was observed as increased viscosity due to reduced particle stability (Fig. 5B), although this increased interparticle attraction was not sufficient to cause agglomeration of the particles, thus maintaining the size of particles present in the absence of synthetic pore fluid, as observed in the UV/vis curves in Fig. 7B. Fig. 9 summarises all three tailored Mt systems different behavioural mechanisms at high pH (pH 13). The FTIR results (Fig. 10), the sample with highest arbitrary 'wetness', that is, the largest Si—O—OH peak in the FTIR analysis, was the HPS inorganic-tailored which showed a consistent high wettability when the pH ranged from 7 to 13. Reference-slurry appeared to show less —OH association, although it is not clear if this difference is significant. The XDB organo-tailored exhibited the lowest 'wetness'. This is unsurprising given the hydrophobic characteristic inherited from the organo modifier. There was an increase in viscosity of the XDB organo-tailored, whereas HPS inorganic-tailored Mt was less viscous indicating that the surfactant NaPA may be preventing the gelation of the dispersion.

4. Conclusions

For the first time an analytical protocol was used to live-monitor the behaviour of three different tailored Mt nanoparticles in synthetic cement pore fluid (pH of 12–13). It can be concluded that:

Fig. 10. Comparison of the wetness of the three tailored Mt nanoparticles (7–13) pH environment.

- (i) Mt needs to be tailored to the alkaline environment in order to remain as discrete nanoparticles in the cement paste.
- (ii) The potential for Mt nanoparticle to act as a nucleation agent will be affected by its nature (inorganic or organic); and ability to remain dispersed in the alkaline environment;
- (iii) Inorganic-tailored Mt nanoparticles showed higher compatibility and dispersion stability than organo-tailored Mt nanoparticles in synthetic cement pore fluid.
- (iv) Organo modification of the Mt nanoparticles can have an adverse effect on dispersion causing agglomeration rather than exfoliation. Therefore organo modification needs to be carried out rigorously.
- (v) Surfactant alters dispersion stability and compatibility of the Mt nanoparticles in synthetic cement pore fluid.
- (vi) The optimum dispersion stability ratio between surfactant and Mt nanoparticle can be obtained by monitoring the effect of surfactant to Mt nanoparticles ratio upon viscosity at low and intermediate shear rate.

This much improved understanding of the behaviour of the Mt nanoparticles in a hydrating alkaline cement environment has shown that inorganic Mt nanoparticles have the same potential as organomodified Mt nanoparticles in regards to nucleation of CSH. Furthermore, because organo modification has now been shown to be unnecessary to provide nucleation behaviour these benefits are provided at a lower carbon footprint.

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